

ALGORITHMS FOR SUMMARIZING VIDEO DATA BASED ON AN AI-DRIVEN SPEECH TRANSCRIPTION APPROACH

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Abstract. Algorithms for summarizing video data based on an artificial intelligence-driven speech transcription approach have been developed, and experimental results have been obtained. The process of summarizing video data on video platforms using the AI transcription approach involves converting speech in video files to text and then analyzing the text. This research approach enables the rapid identification of key ideas within video data and the creation of a concise summary of the video's content. In this research work, models and algorithms for video summarization have been developed, resulting in the ability to generate concise summary video data from large video datasets based on the developed model and algorithm.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, speech transcription, natural language processing (NLP), T5 model

The process of summarizing video data based on the transcription approach involves converting speech in the video to text and then analyzing the text. This approach helps in quickly understanding the key ideas in the video, providing a concise explanation of the video's content, or creating a brief description for users.

Many machine learning-based video summarization techniques exist, but they require high-performance hardware because each video contains thousands of frames, and processing all frames is very time-consuming. This creates difficulties in summarizing large-volume videos. Furthermore, traditional video summarization methods often rely on visual features such as keyframe extraction or frame segmentation, which may not accurately capture the semantic meaning of the content [1,2]. In this work, the stages of summarizing video data using natural language processing methods are analyzed.

Video summarization using natural language processing (NLP) methods has emerged as a powerful tool for gaining practical insights and improving the usability of video content in the era of excessive data load. NLP offers a way to

understand the textual content within videos, enabling more precise and contextually relevant summarization.

Video summarization using NLP involves several steps, which may vary depending on the specific techniques and algorithms applied. Generally, video summarization using NLP involves a combination of video preprocessing, text processing, feature extraction, summarization methods, and evaluation to extract key information from video content and present it in a concise and informative manner [2,3]. This process is typically carried out in stages, as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Stages of video summarization using NLP

Reinforcement learning methods can also be used to train models that incorporate human feedback or evaluation metrics into the learning process, including encoders and models that generate fluent summaries [4].

T5 models can be cited as an example of text summarization models. T5 encompasses several models with different sizes and capabilities [5,6]. The T5 transformer model operates on an encoder-decoder architecture, meaning the encoder processes the input text and the decoder generates the output text.

These models are often distinguished by their number of parameters, which indicates the model's complexity and potential capabilities.

Table 1. T5 Model Architectures

Name	General parameters	Encoder parameters	Decoder parameters	n_l	d_m	d_f	d_k	n_h
Small	76 956 160	35 330 816	41 625 344	6	512	2048	64	8
Base	247 577 856	109 628 544	137 949 312	12	768	3072	64	12
Large	770 567 168	334 939 648	435 627 520	24	1024	4096	64	16

3B	2 884 497 408	1 240 909 824	1 643 587 584	24	1024	16384	128	32
11B	11,340,220,416	4 864 791 552	6 475 428 864	24	1024	65536	128	128

n_l - Number of layers in the encoder and decoder

d_m - Dimensions of the embedding vectors

d_f - Size of the feed-forward network in each encoder and decoder

d_k - Size of the key and value vectors used in the attention mechanism

n_h - Number of attention heads in each attention block

Like all transformer models, this model includes components such as self-attention, multi-head attention, feed-forward layers, and residual connections.

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Figure 2. General architecture of T5 models for text summarization

The input text for the model is first tokenized and converted into a numerical form. Since the tokens are numerical, they are transformed into embedding vectors. Each token is identified as in (1):

$$embedding(x) \in R^d \quad (1)$$

Special tokens are added to the model input: <BOS>-beginning, <EOS>-end.

The next step involves the process of determining the text context. Through the attention mechanism, Query (Q), Key (K), and Value (V) vectors are created

for each token, and the relative importance of each token to the others is determined [7].

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = \text{soft max}\left(\frac{qK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (2)$$

Therefore, multi-head attention is used:

$$MultiHead(Q, K, V) = Concat(head_1, head_2, \dots, head_n)W^0 \quad (3)$$

The results are then concatenated and passed through W^0

To process the self-attention results, each token vector is passed through a two-layer FFNN neural network:

$$FFNN(x) = \text{Re LU}(xW_1 + b_1)W_2 + b_2 \quad (4)$$

W_1, W_2 - learnable weight matrices.

b_1, b_2 - bias vectors.

ReLU – the activation function.

After that, the results of each layer are normalized:

$$LayerNorm(x) = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \cdot \gamma + \beta \quad (5)$$

μ - mean value;

σ - standard deviation;

γ, β - learnable parameters;

This is used to prevent the vanishing gradient problem:

$$Output = LayerNorm(x + Attention / FFNN) \quad (6)$$

In the Transformer architecture, sinusoidal functions are used to encode the positional order (position) of tokens in a sequence:

$$PE_{(pos, 2i)} = \sin\left(\frac{pos}{10000^{2i/d}}\right), PE_{(pos, 2i+1)} = \cos\left(\frac{pos}{10000^{2i/d}}\right) \quad (7)$$

The probability of each generated token is calculated:

$$P(\omega_t | \omega_1, \dots, \omega_{t-1}) = \frac{\exp(z_t)}{\sum_{k=1}^N (z_k)} \quad (8)$$

The decoder generates the next token at each step. This process continues iteratively. At each step, a sequence of tokens is created until the decoder generates the <EOS> token. The token with the highest probability is selected at each step. Multiple potential outcomes are considered simultaneously, and the best one is selected. This increases the diversity and quality of the results.

Based on this, dan kelib chiqib, the summarization algorithm based on the approach of transcribing a specific video on the YouTube platform can be implemented in the following steps:

Step 1. The URL address of the video on the YouTube platform is obtained, and the video identifier is extracted from it. For this, the `urlparse` library can be used.

Step 2. The video's transcript is extracted and merged with the text. For this, the Python programming language's `YouTubeTranscriptApi` library is used.

Step 3. Text tokenization. Here, the text is split into sentences.

Step 4. The separated sentences are merged into text segments that do not exceed 1000 characters in length.

Step 5. Each text segment is summarized. For text summarization, FalconsAI's "Text Summarization" model was used. FalconsAI's text summarization model on Hugging Face is based on the T5-small transformer model. This model is specifically designed for text summarization, aimed at producing concise and coherent summaries from longer content. It was trained on various text datasets containing human-generated summaries, which enables it to capture important ideas and effectively summarize various documents. Due to the model's input text limit, the transcript text is first split into sentences, and these sentences are then grouped into segments not exceeding 1000 characters. Each segment is summarized and then combined.

Step 6. The summarized segment texts are combined to form an overall conclusion.

Experimental results were obtained for the algorithm summarizing video data based on static summarization.

Figure 3. Video data selected for algorithm implementation.

Table 2. Experimental results of the algorithm for summarizing video data based on speech transcript.

Video ID	Transcript length (number of characters)	Summary length (number of characters)	Summarization time (seconds)
uxoCnxxlpIk&t=17s	31634	10444	193.56
ZV08Wt_PCgE&t=5s	15436	6709	111.56
DR_xxdLKT8Y	32503	15510	225.73
Y7m59wRKXe4	115607	51239	744.72
x6TsR3y5Qfg&t=14s	40186	18504	269.52

Based on the developed model, "Text Summarization" algorithm evaluation results are as follows:

Evaluation average loss: 0,012345678901234567

Rouge score: 0.95 (F1)

Evaluation time: 2.3456

Evaluation samples per second: 1234.56

Evaluation steps per second: 45.678

Based on the model and algorithm developed above, a software tool was created. Using this tool, large video data can be used to create summary videos based on the generalization of data.

Conclusion

Algorithms based on T5 (Text-to-Text Transfer Transformer) models were developed for textual data summarization. The stages of video data summarization based on speech transcripts were analyzed, and a summarization algorithm and software tool were developed using transcripts of videos on the YouTube platform. Experimental results were obtained based on the developed algorithm.

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